

Composite Origami for Fluidic Artificial Muscles

Michael P. M. Dicker^{1,2*}, Simon Bates^{1,2}, Steve Grey¹, Tom Llewellyn-Jones^{1,2} and Mark Schenk¹

¹ Advanced Composites Centre for Innovation and Science (ACCIS), University of Bristol, UK, ² Actuation Lab Ltd, Bristol, UK

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Overview

- Background
 - Fluidic Artificial Muscles and McKibben Devices
 - Origami Bellows
- Contractile Origami Bellows Design
 - Origami Tessellations
 - Bellows Models
- 3D Printed Actuators
- Composite Origami
- Composite Actuators

Artificial Muscles

- Actuators are the muscles that make machines move.
- Linear actuators are generally either electric motor driven screws or fluid (hydraulic/pneumatic) driven cylinders.
- Artificial muscles can be defined as “solid-state” actuators, devoid of discrete components and traditional sliding connection.
- Huge range of different devices e.g. dielectric elastomer, thermal twisted and coiled polymers or fluid powered elastomeric systems.
- Common type are “McKibben” style fluidic devices.

McKibben Fluidic Artificial Muscles

FESTO Fludic muscle
https://www.festo.com/ca/en_gb/products_010606

Issues and Limitations

- Very high materials strain for operation ($>50\%$)
- Challenge to withstand pressure during operation
- Max 4 MPa reported
- But typical hydraulic pressure ~ 20 MPa
- While specific power good, can't compete on power density.

Mori M, Suzumori K, Takahashi M and Hosoya T 2010 Very High Force Hydraulic McKibben Artificial Muscle with a p-Phenylene-2,6-benzobisoxazole Cord Sleeve *Adv. Robot.* **24** 233–54

Origami Fluidic Bellows

- Potential for smaller local strains for large global deformation

Li S and Wang K W 2015 Fluidic origami: a plant-inspired adaptive structure with shape morphing and stiffness tuning *Smart Mater. Struct.* **24**

Li S and Wang K W 2015 Fluidic origami with embedded pressure dependent multi-stability: a plant inspired innovation *J. R. Soc. Interface* **12** 20150639

Bogunyà Piferrer V 2016 The waterbomb actuator: a new origami-based pneumatic soft muscle

Sane H, Bhowad P and Li S 2018 Actuation performance of fluidic origami cellular structure: a holistic investigation *Smart Mater. Struct.* **27** 115014

Need for Contraction

- If extends against load when actuated, then membrane structure susceptible to buckle, limited force.
- Vacuum operation possible, but max pressure just 1 bar

Li S, Vogt D M, Rus D and Wood R J 2017 Fluid-driven origami-inspired artificial muscles *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **114** 13132–7

Origami Bellows McKibben

Desire to replicate the composite *material* properties (e.g. Poisson's Ratio) of the McKibben Actuator, with a equivalent *structural* origami tessellation.

McKibben to Origami Bellows Design

Work from Ideal Geometry

$$V = \pi r^2 l = \pi r_0^2 l_0 [(1 - \varepsilon) f^2] \quad F(l) = - \frac{dV}{dl} P$$

$$F_{\text{ideal cyl}}(\mu) = \frac{P}{4\pi N^2} [3\lambda_2^2 l_0^2 - B^2]$$

Anisotropic Composite

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_\phi \end{Bmatrix} = [\mathbf{A}]^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{P_{os} r}{2} \\ P_{os} r \end{Bmatrix}$$

Tondu, B. (2012). Modelling of the McKibben artificial muscle: A review. *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, 23(3), 225–253.

McKibben to Origami Bellows Design

Miura

- Auxetic, Poisson's ratio < 0

Eggbox

- Poisson's ratio > 0

Schenk, Mark and Simon D. Guest.
 "Origami folding: A Structural
 Engineering Approach." (2011).

Eggbox Origami Bellows – Bar and Hinge

Modified MERLIN MATLAB implementation of origami bar and hinge mode.

$P=0.2$ MPa

Filipov E T, Liu K, Tachi T, Schenk M and Paulino G H 2017 Bar and hinge models for scalable analysis of origami *Int. J. Solids Struct.* **124** 26–45

Liu K and Paulino G H 2017 Nonlinear mechanics of non-rigid origami: an efficient computational approach *Proc. R. Soc. A Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.* **473** 20170348

UK patent filed 14th of June 2019

ABAQUS FEA

ABAQUS FEA

Additive Manufacturing

Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU) Printing

Printed Performance

$P = 0.03$ MPa, 20 kg force from
120 g Actuator

But need higher absolute load and
force density

Composite Origami

White. C. 2016. "Manufacturing and Structural Characterization of Flexible and Dual-Matrix Deployable Composites for Space Application." North Carolina State University Thesis

Gay A M 2017 *Fabrication and Classification of Dual-Matrix Composites for Deployable Space Applications* (North Carolina State University)

Composite Origami

FIG. 1

Mike Malia, Brian Kaplun D C 2013
Composite Live Hinge
US20150040349A1

Tile		Tile
CFRP	Crest	CFRP
	GF + Urethane	
CFRP		CFRP

<https://www.carbonhinge.com/> Talon

O'NEIL J, DELEO A, 2018
Deployable Structures
Constructed from
Composite Origami *dpi-*
proceedings.com

J. M. Mejia-Ariza "Mechanical characterization of L'Garde elastomeric resin composite materials," 51st AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, AIAA, Orlando, FL, 2010. 95

I. Maqueda "Characterization of a high strain composite material," 53rd AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, AIAA, Honolulu, HI, 2012.

Michael Dicker

Composites Origami McKibben

Conclusions

- Challenging to operate high material strain composite artificial muscles at high pressure, thus poor power density.
- Origami bellows may allow higher pressure, but a new contractile design was required.
- New design implemented in TPU 3D printing.
- 200 N force at 0.03 MPa pressure from 0.12 kg actuator.
- First prototypes of composite version presented in quest to engineer hydraulic pressure capable actuator with high power density.

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